

Knowledge, Attitude, and Practices on Solid Waste Management Among Residents of a Riverside Barangay: Basis for Sustainable Policies and Programs

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Abstract

A descriptive-correlational study was conducted among 350 residents of Barangay Consolacion, Cagayan de Oro, Philippines, to assess their Knowledge, Attitude, and Practices (KAP) regarding Solid Waste Management (SWM) and how these relate to their actual waste management behaviors. The main goal was to understand the residents' level of awareness about SWM, their attitudes toward it, and how these factors influence their everyday practices. Data were gathered through surveys, and statistical tools, including Pearson correlation, were applied to identify connections between the variables. The findings showed that residents had moderate knowledge of SWM, with awareness of programs (mean = 3.27), environmental issues (mean = 3.32), and the importance of training (mean = 3.41). Positive attitudes were observed in areas like waste separation (mean = 3.17), labeling (mean = 3.32), and volunteerism (mean = 3.29). However, there were gaps in actual practices, such as waste collection methods and disposal consistency, which indicated room for improvement. Alarmingly, open waste burning was still somewhat prevalent (mean = 2.90). The study revealed strong positive correlations between residents' knowledge, attitudes, and their SWM practices, suggesting that enhancing residents' awareness and attitudes could lead to better waste management behaviors. Ultimately, the study calls for targeted interventions to improve practices, including more emphasis on recycling, composting, and community education to foster long-term sustainable waste management.

Keywords: *Community engagement, Environmental sustainability, Knowledge attitude, and practices (KAP), Solid waste management (SWM), Waste disposal practices*

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Introduction

Each year, the world generates around 11.2 billion tons of solid waste, and the decomposition of organic materials in this waste contributes to about 5% of global greenhouse gas emissions.

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Improper disposal of this waste can lead to a range of harmful consequences: the spread of diseases, air and water pollution, rising greenhouse gas levels, and respiratory problems. Thus, understanding how people perceive and manage solid waste is essential. Studies focused on knowledge, attitudes, and practices regarding waste disposal can reveal gaps in public awareness and behaviors that lead to improper disposal. By identifying these gaps, stakeholders will be able to develop targeted educational campaigns and policies to foster more sustainable waste management practices. This approach not only helps mitigate environmental damage but also improves public health by reducing the harmful effects associated with waste mismanagement.

According to Zoleta and Nawang (2015), the primary sources of organic pollution are from residential, commercial, and industrial areas. This suggests that solid waste management strategies should focus on these areas to reduce pollution. It was proved in the study of Zoleta and Almaraz (2023) that improper solid waste management has risks to the environment, including bodies of water. Their study's findings of the Cagayan de Oro River revealed exceedances in phosphate concentrations and total coliform counts, which underscored the pressing need for improved solid waste management practices. In the Philippines, solid waste disposal poses a significant challenge, with the country generating around 35,580 tons of garbage daily (Castillo & Otoma, 2013). This ineffective management is exacerbated by high plastic demand, a lack of waste disposal facilities, inadequate waste collection, and insufficient public awareness (Manas, 2023). The environmental and health impacts are severe; for instance, the Philippines is one of the top contributors to global ocean plastic pollution, with an estimated 0.75 million metric tons of plastic waste entering the ocean annually (Jambeck et al., 2015). This pollution not only degrades marine ecosystems but also poses health risks to communities, including increased incidences of vector-borne diseases and respiratory issues due to air and water pollution. It was also emphasized by Campanale et al. (2020) that microplastics pose a significant health concern as they can be ingested by humans and may have far-reaching implications for physical well-being by affecting various systems and sensitive areas within the body.

Waste management continues to be a major challenge for cities worldwide (Matthews, 2019). According to World Bank (2018), the global generation of municipal waste totals 2.01 billion tons annually, with at least one-third of this waste being managed in ways that do not meet environmental safety standards. On average, each person produces 0.74 kilograms of waste per day, although this figure varies significantly across regions, ranging from 0.11 to 4.54 kilograms (Wu, 2023). High-income countries, which constitute just 16 percent of the global population, are responsible for approximately 34 percent of global waste, totaling 683 million tons. Projections indicate that by 2050, global waste generation will rise to 3.40 billion tons, more than double the anticipated growth of the global population. A clear correlation exists between income levels and waste production, with per capita waste in high-income countries expected to increase by 19 percent, while in low- and middle-income countries, the increase could exceed 40 percent. Although waste generation is lower in the poorest regions, it rises more rapidly as income increases, and by 2050, low-income countries are projected to more than triple their waste output.

The Knowledge, Attitude, and Practices (KAP) are interconnected components crucial for effective waste management. Knowledge refers to the information individuals possess about waste management practices, such as sorting, recycling, and proper disposal methods. Attitude pertains to individuals' feelings, beliefs, and perceptions towards waste management, which influence their willingness to engage in sustainable behaviors. Practices involve the actual behaviors and actions individuals undertake, like segregating recyclables or reducing single-use plastics. A study conducted by Lema et al. (2019) construed that households' perceptions, awareness, knowledge, attitudes, and behaviors regarding solid waste management (SWM) play a crucial role in shaping its

effectiveness, while research by Smith (2021) highlighted the role of attitude in shaping individuals' willingness to adopt sustainable waste management behaviors.

Despite ongoing efforts to improve waste management, Cagayan de Oro continues to face significant challenges. Recently, 40 out of 80 Barangays were warned for not complying with the solid waste management law. The City Local Environment and Natural Resources Office (CLENRO) granted these Barangays a 15-day extension, stressing that stricter enforcement would be implemented moving forward. Barangay leaders have been instructed to create local ordinances and form committees to ensure proper waste management (Rosete, 2024). This renewed push for compliance comes nearly 25 years after the law was first enacted, signaling the city's ongoing commitment to addressing waste management issues. In certain areas, like riverside Barangays, the need for effective waste management is particularly urgent, as improper waste disposal directly pollutes the river, affecting water quality, aquatic life, and the health of residents living along the riverbanks. In these communities, proper waste segregation and collection are not just legal obligations but essential for environmental protection and public health.

However, the issue of waste management goes beyond just following the law. As noted by Raghu and Rodrigues (2020), drawing on Sommers (2011) study, the problem is deeply rooted in behavior, with past practices shaping the current state of the environment. This is evident in Barangay settings as well, where despite efforts like color-coded bins, a Materials Recovery Facility (MRF), and awareness campaigns, waste management issues persist. Problems during waste collection and sorting often arise, with insufficient segregation requiring additional sorting at the MRF. This gap in awareness and compliance highlights the need for a deeper understanding of the behavioral factors influencing waste management practices, suggesting that tackling the issue requires not only stricter enforcement but also a cultural shift in how waste is viewed and managed.

This study endeavored to articulate the pressing issues on Solid Waste Management by looking at the behavioral aspect, through the lens of a riverside Barangay SWM program. In particular, this study aimed to assess their Knowledge, Attitudes, and Practices (KAP) related to solid waste management in Barangay Consolacion—one of the riverside Barangays in Cagayan de Oro, and explored the relationships between these factors and effective waste management practices. By highlighting the behavioral aspects that influence solid waste management—supported by findings from Raghu and Rodrigues (2020)—the research contributed to developing targeted interventions that promote awareness, sustainable practices, and community engagement. Ultimately, the study sought to inform strategies that can significantly improve waste management outcomes, mitigate pollution, and foster a healthier environment for future generations.

Framework

The study aimed to measure the knowledge, attitude, and practices (KAP) of solid waste management among residents. Fishbein and Ajzen (1975) developed the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA), which served as the foundation for the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB). According to TPB, individuals act rationally based on their attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control, which collectively shape their intentions and ultimately, their behaviors (Kim et al., 2024). By applying this theory, the study could effectively evaluate the residents of Barangay Consolacion's current KAP by examining their attitudes towards waste management, the subjective norms they perceived from their social environment, and their perceived control over their ability to manage solid waste (Wang et al., 2017).

Knowledge

Knowledge referred to the understanding and awareness of solid waste management principles. This was measured through awareness programs, environmental topics, and training. Awareness programs and training sessions were crucial in educating the community about waste reduction

strategies, recycling methods, and the environmental impacts of waste. Environmental topics covered a broad range of issues related to waste management, providing the community with a comprehensive understanding of the subject (Moh & Manaf, 2017).

Attitude

Attitude encompassed the perceptions and beliefs towards waste management practices. This included attitudes towards waste separation, labeling, information sharing, and volunteerism. Positive attitudes towards waste separation and labeling were essential for effective waste management. Information sharing and volunteerism were also critical as they promoted community engagement and participation in waste management initiatives (Uwamwezi, 2015).

Practices

Practices referred to the actions taken by the community in managing waste. This included waste collection, waste transportation, and disposal methods. Effective waste collection and transportation systems were crucial for managing waste efficiently. Proper disposal methods ensured that waste was handled in an environmentally friendly manner (Uwamwezi, 2015).

Solid waste management

Solid waste management referred to the entire process of collecting, transporting, treating and disposing of waste within the Barangay. Effective solid waste management was characterized by proper disposal methods, designated collection points, regulatory compliance, and the management of infectious/hazardous waste. Proper disposal methods ensured that waste was handled safely and responsibly (Uwamwezi, 2015). Designated collection points facilitated the efficient collection and transportation of waste. Regulatory compliance ensured that waste management practices adhered to legal and environmental standards (Moh & Manaf, 2017). The management of infectious/hazardous waste was critical for preventing health and environmental hazards (Gupta et al., 2023).

Objectives

This study aimed to explore the critical challenges in solid waste management, focusing specifically on the behavioral aspects, through the lens of a riverside Barangay's waste management program. The research centered on assessing the Knowledge, Attitudes, and Practices (KAP) regarding solid waste management in Barangay Consolacion, a riverside community in Cagayan de Oro City, Philippines. Additionally, it sought to understand how these factors are connected to the effectiveness of waste management practices within the Barangay.

Methodology

The study used a descriptive-correlational research design to assess the Knowledge, Attitudes and Practices (KAP) of residents on solid waste management. This design integrated descriptive aspects, which aimed to summarize and measure KAP levels and trends, with correlational components. The correlational components explored how different factors were interconnected within their natural environment, without any interference from the researcher (Bhandari, 2021). The descriptive-correlational design is practical for surveying large groups and effective for describing and exploring relationships, although it may not prove causation. Correlations might be positive (factors changed similarly) or negative (factors changed oppositely), but may imply direct causality. The insights gained may be valuable for informing the decisions of policymakers and stakeholders.

This study followed a meticulous data collection process with a strong emphasis on ethics, participant welfare, and data quality. A finalized questionnaire, developed through expert feedback and pilot testing, was the primary tool for gathering reliable responses. Ethical approval was secured from the university's ethics board, and permissions were obtained from both the dean and the Barangay office to align with institutional and local policies. Preliminary data was gathered to assess the current state of solid waste management in Barangay Consolacion, alongside demographic details from adult residents. Key community leaders, such as zone leaders, assisted with logistics and identifying eligible participants. An orientation session was held to explain the study's purpose and ethical considerations, ensuring participants fully understood their involvement. Data collection prioritized participant autonomy, with voluntary participation and the ability to withdraw at any time. All responses were anonymized, and data was securely stored and deleted post-study. Ethical standards were maintained throughout, with clear informed consent and privacy protections. The study's goal was to gain insights into solid waste management practices by assessing residents' knowledge, attitudes, and behaviors, identifying gaps, and informing interventions to improve waste management and address health impacts from improper waste disposal. Community engagement was key, with minimal disruption to daily routines, and the findings were shared with the Barangay council and local stakeholders to foster evidence-based decisions and action. Finally, participants were thanked with small tokens, ensuring that the study respected their dignity while producing meaningful, actionable results for the community's sustainability efforts.

The study targeted adult residents aged 18-59 of Barangay Consolacion, Cagayan de Oro City, Philippines. A simple random sampling method was used to ensure unbiased selection, giving everyone an equal chance of being chosen. The sample size was calculated using Slovin's formula: $(n = N / 1 + Ne^2)$ (Slovin, 1960), where n is the sample size, N is the total population, and e is the error tolerance. This approach ensured a representative, random sample without pre-existing biases or patterns, aiming for accurate insights reflective of the community's diversity.

Results and Discussion

This study endeavored to articulate the pressing issues on Solid Waste Management by looking at the behavioral aspect, through the lens of a riverside Barangay SWM program. In particular, this study aimed to assess their Knowledge, Attitudes, and Practices (KAP) related to solid waste management in Barangay Consolacion—one of the riverside Barangays in Cagayan de Oro City Philippines, and explored the relationships between these factors and the waste management practices.

Residents of Barangay Consolacion demonstrated a moderate level of knowledge about Solid Waste Management (SWM), particularly in areas such as awareness programs (mean = 3.27), environmental issues (mean = 3.32), and training (mean = 3.41). They generally agreed that they attend awareness programs (mean = 3.22) and understand their roles in SWM (mean = 3.32), likely due to partnerships with the Safer River Life Saver Foundation and compliance with RA 9003. Their understanding of environmental issues, such as pollution sources (mean = 3.45) and waste minimization (mean = 3.26), was also moderate, reflecting the effectiveness of periodic Information, Education, and Communication (IEC) initiatives. Training on SWM was recognized as important, with residents agreeing on the need for more training (mean = 3.41) and the use of protective clothing (mean = 3.37).

The residents exhibited a generally positive attitude towards SWM, particularly in areas like waste separation (mean = 3.17), labeling (mean = 3.32), information sharing (mean = 3.18), and volunteerism (mean = 3.29). They acknowledged the importance of separating waste (mean =

3.16), having clear labels on garbage bins (mean = 3.31), and sharing SWM information (mean = 3.12). Volunteerism was also viewed positively, with residents willing to participate in recycling initiatives (mean = 3.26) and forums (mean = 3.29). This positive outlook is likely influenced by Barangay officials' active engagement in disseminating SWM information, which aligns with previous studies showing the impact of accurate information on public perceptions and behaviors.

Regarding SWM practices, residents found waste collection (mean = 3.28), transportation (mean = 3.26), and disposal methods (mean = 3.10) to be generally effective, although they acknowledged room for improvement. They reported satisfaction with qualified personnel (mean = 3.30), effective waste collection (mean = 3.33), and professional waste transportation (mean = 3.26). However, concerns about open burning of waste (mean = 2.90) highlighted the need for more sustainable practices. Residents were satisfied with proper disposal methods (mean = 3.24), designated collection points (mean = 3.27), regulatory compliance (mean = 3.17), and the handling of infectious or hazardous waste (mean = 3.11).

Overall, residents rated waste disposal practices as good, with an average mean score of 3.24. They appreciated the proper disposal of waste in designated bins (mean = 3.26) and the reliability of scheduled waste collection (mean = 3.30), suggesting a well-organized system. However, the slightly lower score of 3.17 for waste management indicates some areas for improvement. Strengths of the system include proper disposal methods, regulatory compliance, and accessible collection points (mean = 3.27). Residents also viewed the handling of infectious and hazardous waste positively (mean = 3.11), reflecting confidence in the barangay's capacity to manage such materials safely. However, the issue of open burning (mean = 2.90) calls for more sustainable alternatives, such as expanding recycling programs, promoting composting, and enhancing public education.

The study also revealed a significant relationship between residents' knowledge, attitudes, and practices concerning SWM. Pearson correlation analysis showed strong positive correlations among these variables, with significant p-values ($p < .000$), leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. This suggests that improving residents' knowledge and attitudes toward SWM can positively influence their practices, ultimately enhancing the effectiveness of the barangay's SWM system.

Conclusions

The study concludes that the residents of Barangay Consolacion, Cagayan de Oro, in the Philippines, demonstrate a moderate level of knowledge and a generally positive attitude towards solid waste management (SWM), largely attributable to awareness programs and training initiatives. This underscores the effectiveness of educational efforts in shaping community perceptions and behaviors. Residents actively engage in waste separation, segregation, labeling, information sharing, and volunteerism, reflecting a proactive approach to waste management. However, areas such as regular waste control and open burning require further attention to enhance overall effectiveness.

The observations of the residents with current waste disposal practices and the barangay's adherence to regulatory standards highlight a foundational level of compliance and community support. The significant relationship identified between residents' knowledge, attitudes, practices, and the barangay's SWM practices emphasizes the need for targeted interventions. These interventions should aim to enhance awareness, promote sustainable practices, and foster community engagement, thereby improving waste management outcomes and mitigating pollution for a healthier environment.

Investing in educational initiatives and community programs is essential to further elevate the knowledge and attitudes of residents, ensuring that waste management practices are not only

effective but also sustainable. By addressing specific areas of improvement and encouraging continuous community involvement, Barangay Consolacion can achieve more robust and environmentally sound waste management practices, contributing to a cleaner and healthier community.

Recommendations

Based on the results of the study, the researcher would like to recommend the following:

1. For residents, it is highly recommended to actively participate in educational campaigns on waste management, segregate waste at the source using color-coded bins, avoid open burning by adopting composting and recycling, share best practices with neighbors, and volunteer in community clean-up drives and recycling initiatives
2. For the barangay officials, it is recommended to enhance existing training programs such as on conducting IEC and lectures on waste minimization. Initiatives such as mandatory waste segregation, bans on open burning, community recycling programs, composting initiatives, optimized waste collection services, regularly review and update waste management policies, and continuously monitor and evaluate waste management practices.
3. Educational institutions can integrate the study's findings into their curricula to educate students about the importance of waste management. Schools and universities can develop modules and lessons on waste segregation, recycling, and composting, and incorporate these into science and environmental studies courses.
4. Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) focused on environmental conservation and sustainability can use the study's insights to design more targeted campaigns and initiatives. NGOs can collaborate with local authorities and residents to implement sustainable waste management solutions, such as community recycling programs and composting initiatives.
5. For the private sector, they can benefit from the study by adopting more sustainable waste management practices, which can enhance their corporate social responsibility (CSR) initiatives. Businesses should implement waste segregation and recycling programs within their operations and promote these practices among their employees.
6. For the City Local Environment and Natural Resources Office (CLENRO), it is recommended that conducting surveys and gathering feedback can provide valuable insights to inform policy adjustments. Strengthening enforcement, improving infrastructure, and leveraging technology can optimize waste collection and disposal. Collaborating with local organizations and the private sector, along with implementing incentive programs, can further drive sustainable practices and community participation.
7. Future researchers can conduct longitudinal studies on educational campaigns and policy changes, assess behavioral factors influencing waste management, evaluate policy effectiveness, engage with stakeholders, and develop targeted interventions based on research findings. Studies can explore people's motivations for engaging in solid waste management and consider demographic profiles to better understand waste management practices.

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